

EARTH SCIENCES

ECOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF HYDROLOGICAL MONUMENTS OF SHEKI-ZAGATALA REGION

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Abstract

The presented article examines hydrological monuments located in Sheki-Zagatala region. These monuments include rivers, lakes and waterfalls. In modern times, there are a number of environmental problems related to water resources. It is these environmental problems that greatly affect the ecotourism sector of the Sheki-Zagatala region.

Keywords: *Azerbaijan Republic, Sheki-Zagatala region, hydrological monuments, ecology, ecotourism*

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Introduction

It is known that the basis of the world is water. Water is the basis of life. Like many countries around the world, the Republic of Azerbaijan is very rich in this regard. The presence of rivers, lakes and waterfalls indicates the abundance of water resources in the country. The Sheki-Zagatala region is very rich in this regard. The presence of every hydrological monument in the area has a positive impact on the development of the ecotourism sector in the region. However, these monuments have many ecological problems. The relevance of the article is to discuss the role of these hydrological monuments in the Sheki-Zagatala region in the ecotourism sector. The object of research is rivers, lakes and waterfalls in the region. The subject of the study is the ecological mechanisms of hydrological monuments of the Sheki-Zagatala region. The main purpose and task of the research is to provide information about these hydrological monuments located in the region and to study their ecological problems, as well as to show the usefulness of monuments for the ecological tourism sector.

Hydrological monuments in Sheki-Zagatala region

As we know, Sheki-Zagatala region is rich in natural resources. In each of the districts of the Sheki-Zagatala region, there are hydrological monuments, or more precisely, rivers, lakes and waterfalls. Thus, the hydrological monuments of the region can be divided as follows:

✓ Rivers – Turyanchay, Damiraparanchay, Tikanlichay, Bum, Vandam (Gabala), Khalkhal, Dashagil, Oghuz, Turyanchay, Galachay (Oghuz), Alijan, Kishchay, Shin (Shaki), Ganikh /Alazan, Kumruk, Ayrichay (Gakh), Talachay (Zagatala), Balakan, Mazim, Khatekh, Ganikh / Ayrichay (Balakan);

✓ Lakes – Nohurgol, Tufangol, Turfangol (Gabala) and Ajinohur (Gakh);

✓ Waterfalls – Ramrama, Lakit, Shahverdi, İlisu, Gochyataghi, Mamirli (Gakh), Yeddi Gozal, Mujugh (Gabala), Khatekhchay (Balakan) and etc.

Khatekhchay waterfall is considered to be the most famous and the most abundant waterfall in Azerbaijan and is included in the territory of Zagatala State Nature Reserve, its height is about 20 meters. Yeddi Gozal Waterfalls is located on the side of the Oguz-Gabala road. İlisu waterfall in Gakh is located in the highest part of the region and its height is about 25 meters. Another waterfall in Gakh is Mamirli waterfall, located in the forest above the village of Lakit. The locals call this waterfall Damchi waterfall (Mammadov, 2012, pp.209, 223, 231, 239, 250, 258, 267, 279; Mammadov et al, 2015, pp. 658-659).

Figure 1. Khatekhchay (Mammadov, 2012, pp.206)

Problems of hydrological monuments of Sheki-Zagatala region in ecological environment

In addition to being rich in hydrological monuments, the Sheki-Zagatala region also has certain environmental problems. Observations in the region reveal the ecological environment and problems of water resources. In general, the disturbance of this ecological balance leads to the death and reduction of living things living inside hydrological monuments. This creates conditions for the extinction of wildlife. So, there are two main reasons for this problem:

- 1) Natural phenomena;
- 2) Anthropogenic influences.

It is a fact that man is a major figure in the pollution of nature, but also affects the hydrological regime. The influence of the human phenomenon is also observed in the Sheki-Zagatala region. So that, the Ganikh River is located on the border between Azerbaijan and Georgia. In 2015-2016, experts conducted seasonal surveys of the river, and as a result, it was determined that the river was polluted in Georgia. The main reason for this is industrial, agricultural and household waste. Because about 80% of the vineyards of the Republic of

Georgia are located in the Ganikh valley, and there are no sewage treatment plants in the area along this river. As a result, all domestic wastes and sewage from the washing of arable lands flow into the Ganikh river basin. On the border of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Ganikh River is polluted by small tributaries that flow into the river. Turyanchay is considered to be one of the most silty rivers in the country. The ecological environment of the river is polluted by household waste, as well as fertilizers and medicines used in agriculture. As a result, it is one of the anthropogenic impacts on river pollution

(https://azmbi.az/PDF/AMEA%20Mikrobiologiya%200%C4%B0nsti-tunun%20Elmi%20C6%8Fs%C9%99r1%C9%99ri%202017_15_2.pdf)

Another issue is the turbidity of the rivers. It is formed under the influence of many natural factors in the formation of turbidity of rivers. According to experts, it is divided into seven zones due to the turbidity of rivers in the country. Zones IV, V and VII of them fall to the share of Sheki-Zagatala region. This is given in more detail in the following table:

Table 1.

Calculated and recovered values of turbidity in Sheki-Zagatala region

№	Zones	Interval qr/m ³	Riverpoint (Çay məntəqə)	ρ_{natural} ($\rho_{\text{təbii}}$)	Interval qr/m ³	Riverpoint Çay məntəqə	ρ_{natural} ($\rho_{\text{təbii}}$)
1.	Zone IV	200-5000	Khatekhchay-Gabizdere	372	200-500	Khatekhchay-Gabizdere	372
2.	Zone V	500-1000	Gabirri-Khasaman	565	500-1000	Gabirri-Khasaman	565
			Balakanchay-Balakan	860		Balakanchay-Balakan	867
3.	Zone VII	2000-5000	Talachay-Zagatala	3425	2000-5000	Alazan-Ayrichay	2053
			Ayrichay-Mansab	2571		Talachay-Zagatala	3425
			Alazan-Ayrichay	2053		Damarciq-Mansab	2015

(<http://static.bsu.az/w8/Xeberler%20Jurnali/Tebiet%20%202013%20%202/209-216.pdf>)

The whimsical influence of nature affects to some extent every part of the environment. Thus, natural disasters such as floods often occur in the water resources of the Sheki-Zagatala region. The rivers in the Sheki-Zagatala region, depending on the nature of the water regime, have a spring or spring-summer flow regime and belong to the summer-autumn or autumn flood regime. The hydrological phenomenon of floods in the

rivers of the region is very active. Such rivers in the Sheki-Zagatala region include Balakanchay, Khatekhchay, Talachay, Mukhakhchay (Garachay), Kurmukchay, Kishchay, Mazimchay, Alinjanchay (Khalkhalchay), Ayrichay, branches of Turyanchay - Bumchay, Tikanlichay, Damiraparanchay, Akhchachay (Galachay). In general, most floods were

observed in Damiraparanchay, Khatekhchay, Tikanlichay. The consequences of the floods in the Sheki-Zagatala region are enormous. Here are some examples: An accident on the Damarchin (Kishchay) River on June 27, 1982, destroyed two 140-ton stone Marxal bridges and a road during a flood. During another flood on July 15, 1988, one of the two stones was carried under the bridge near the village of Kish and the other a short distance away; The flood in Ayrichay (Dashagilchay) at the beginning of the 20th century caused great damage to the main Dashagil village, and there are 180 tons of stones brought by the flood in the Dashagilchay channel; The flood that passed through Demirparanchay on April 28-29, 1994 damaged 150 million m² roads in Gabala, and on August 13, 1999, the flood that passed through that river again covered the streets in Gabala with mud; As a result of the floods in Balakanchay, Mazimchay, Katekhchay on June 10-11, 1997, 2,500 hectares of grain crops became unusable, about 100 private houses were destroyed, and some administrative buildings were damaged; As a result of the floods in Demirparanchay and Tikanlichay in 16-17.1999, about 70 houses in Gabala were flooded, 18 cattle perished, and the fields were covered with mud; The flood in Kishchay on June 29, 2002 washed away the electric poles in the river basin in Sheki; As a result

of the flood in Shinchay on July 27, 2004, the drinking water supply was disrupted in Sheki, etc. According to Mammadov Magbet's research, the earliest floods in the Sheki-Zagatala region were in 1846 in Shinchay, and the last on August 17, 1999 in Damiraparanchay, a branch of the Turyanchay. However, floods still occur. On September 23, 2021, as a result of heavy rains, floods were observed in Balakanchay, Khatekhchay and Talachay (Mammadov, 2012, pp.101-127; Maharramova, 2008, pp.43-47; <http://web2.anl.az:81/read/page.php?zoom=0&bibid=346323&pno=12>; <https://az.trend.az/azerbaijan/society/3488294.html>).

On the other hand, the lakes and waterfalls in the Sheki-Zagatala region are in danger of drying up. The main reason for this is climate change. The sharp change in climate as a result of global warming is creating these problems. Thus, in 2021, there was a drying of Lake Acinohurgol, a decrease in the water level of waterfalls such as Yeddi Gozel, Ilisu, Mujugh. So, the presence of rainwater can prevent this event (<https://qafqazinfo.az/news/detail/acinohur-golu-niyequruyur-321019>; <https://aqreqator.az/en/cemiyyet/1569614>).

Figure 2. Ajinohurgol (Mammadov, 2012, pp. 239)

The policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan in the protection of the hydrological environment of the Sheki-Zagatala region

One of the main priorities of the successful state policy pursued by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev is the development of the country's regions. So that, the Order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On additional measures to accelerate the socio-economic development of Sheki, Balakan, Gakh and Zagatala districts of the Republic of Azerbaijan" contains a number of laws, the implementation of which is entrusted to Melioration and Water Management OJSC:

- 1) Cleaning of the bed of the Gurjana and Deyirmanarkhi rivers flowing along the center of Sheki and major restoration of the coastal walls;
- 2) Shore protection works on Kishchay, Dashagilchay and Shinchay rivers;
- 3) Shore protection works on Mazimchay, Khatekhchay and Balakanchay rivers;

4) Carrying out shore protection works to protect the "Sumug Qala" monument and the surrounding area in Ilisu State Historical-Cultural Reserve from floods;

5) Shore protection works on Kurmukchay, Zarna and Ganikh rivers;

6) 1548.6 pm shore protection works on the Mukhakh, Tala and Khatekh rivers at the expense of the Asian Development Bank loan.

The Law on Approval of the "State Program of Socio-Economic Development of the Regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2019-2023" dated January 29, 2019 by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev adopted strategic laws for socio-economic development of the country's regions. One of these measures is an important part of the strategy in the regions. Also, the main priority here is to protect the population from floods and floods to ensure the safety of the population. In the state program of socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2019-2023, the regions of the Sheki-Zagatala region are also included in the list of these

measures. Implementation of the planned works has been entrusted to the Ministry of Emergency Situations, “Azerbaijan Amelioration and Water Management” OJSC, local executive power. The decree envisages the continuation of measures for the development of tourism in the Sheki-Zagatala region, as well as in other regions of Azerbaijan, and this State Tourism Agency has been assigned to the local executive power. Taking into account such measures in our country is one of the main steps for the development of ecotourism in the region.

However, various pilot projects have been proposed in our country to address this issue: “Pilot River Basin Management Plan for Alazan / Ganikh River Basin” developed by Jesper Ansbaek, Anatoly Pichugin, Peter Roncak, Vafadar Ismayilov, Farda Imanov and Rafiq Verdiyev and funded by the European Union in October 2011; “Consultations and workshop on assessment of impact on the National Strategy for the Use of Alternative and Renewable Energy Sources in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2015-2020 and defining the scope of analysis at the base level” held on May 12, 2015 in Baku”; A seminar on MSD on the National Water Strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan SEIIE held on June 7-8, 2012 within the framework of EU SI, etc.

In addition, many river protection and restoration projects have been implemented around the world: projects such as Central Europe – REURIS, UK – River Restoration Center (RRC), Berlin (Germany) – Panke

River Restoration, Munich (Germany) – Isar River Restoration, Olomous (Czech Republic) – Morava River Rehabilitation, Teplise (Czech Republic) – Black River Rehabilitation, Durham County (UK) – Skerne River Rehabilitation, Havant (UK) – Hermitage River Rehabilitation, National River Protection Authority in Israel, development of a special program in this field in Russia, etc. (<https://e-qanun.az/framework/12260>; <https://e-qanun.az/framework/41320>; Mammadov et al, 2015, pp.659; İmanov et al, pp.24-32; <https://meteo.az/index.php?ln=az&pg=110>; https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/eia/meetings/2015/May_SEA_workshop_scoping_Baku/12_may.pdf; https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/water/npd/Water_Strategy_Rafiq_Verdiev.pdf)

Determining the importance of hydrological monuments of Sheki-Zagatala region in the ecotourism system

The presence of hydrological monuments in the Sheki-Zagatala region is one of the main factors contributing to the development of the ecotourism sector in the region. It is known that the field of ecotourism presents the pearls of nature to people. It is the pleasant fresh air of the region, as well as the flora and fauna, as well as the presence of hydrological monuments that make the area useful for the tourism sector. Thus, local and foreign guests visit the water resources monuments here.

Figure 3. Mamirli waterfall (Mammadov, 2015, pp. 658)

Thus, one of the charming hydrological monuments of the region is Mamirli waterfall located in Gakh region. This waterfall is located in a forested area above the village and the water flows through the mossy rocks. Many tourists flock here to see this beautiful view. Thus, the village municipality has cleared the roads leading to the waterfall from large stones to ensure their comfort. Also, the area around the waterfall is monitored, and assistance is provided by guides for visitors. Prohibit the special needs of people in this area, as well as bathing or car washing. In addition, drinking water was pumped to the village from here through a pipeline. Mamirli waterfall of Gakh region was renamed as “Natural Monument” by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated August 5, 2006 and is protected by the state.

Another mysterious waterfall of Gakh is Ilisu. This waterfall is located on the highest peak of the region, so it is not easy for him to climb there. To get here, the tourist must walk at least half an hour. However, for those who can not climb to this height, vehicles are organized (Mammadov et al, 2015, pp. 658-659). There are also many visitors to other hydrological monuments in the region. Even those parts have become places that will be suitable for the tourism sector. However, the improper use of these areas by people who migrate to them leads to the destruction of their natural environment. Therefore, the main issue is not to damage the landscape of these hydrological monuments and to protect them seriously in order to attract more tourists to the region. This in itself is of great importance for

Sheki-Zagatala, as well as for the tourism sector of the Republic of Azerbaijan (Nazarova, 2022, pp. 8-9).

Conclusion and suggestions

Finally, let's list the results we received from the article:

- Ecological problems of hydrological monuments in Sheki-Zagatala region are still on the agenda;
- Certain natural and anthropogenic factors damage hydrological monuments in the area;
- Natural disasters damage the agriculture and individual habitats of the regions, as well as the local population, just as hydrological monuments are damaged;
- The force of anthropogenic impacts on the hydrological monuments of the regions is very large. Chemicals, agricultural waste, industrial waste, etc. these include.
- The state policy of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the protection of water resources and the solution of problems in the region, as well as a number of organized projects and programs are of great importance;
- There are environmental problems of hydrological monuments in most countries of the world and international measures are taken on this;
- Damage to the ecological environment of rivers, lakes and waterfalls in the region leads to the destruction of living things within them;
- The availability of river, lake and waterfall type water resources in the region is very important for the ecotourism sector of the region;
- Hydrological monuments in Sheki-Zagatala region are very important for the Azerbaijani ecotourism system;
- Nowadays, these hydrological monuments are used for the tourism sector and are open to local and foreign tourists.

Thus, we consider it expedient to note the following proposals on the protection of Sheki-Zagatala hydrological monuments:

- Study of natural phenomena in the region – Taking into account the natural effects on the Sheki-Zagatala hydrological monuments, it is expedient to continue work on the study of natural disasters and to establish geographical plans for their prevention;
- Carry out awareness-raising activities on the protection of hydrological monuments in the Sheki-Zagatala region – In this process, it is possible to involve the local population, including pupils and students. In this regard, it is possible to hold various educational events;
- Provide tourists with information on the non-pollution of recreation areas – Local and foreign visitors can be informed about the protection of hydrological monuments that have now become recreation centers;
- Strengthening control over hydrological monuments – It is more appropriate to increase special control to prevent pollution in these hydrological monuments, which are also used as recreation areas in modern times;

- Strengthening measures to ensure human safety – It is known that the hydrological monuments of the Sheki-Zagatala region are well-known and dangerous areas. One of the main issues for this is to ensure the safety of foreign citizens, including locals. Therefore, it is appropriate to intensify the work in this direction;

- Increasing the role of monuments in the region in the ecotourism sector – determining the compliance of these monuments with international standards can increase the importance of the Sheki-Zagatala region in the field of ecotourism. For this reason, it would be good to identify tourist activities used in hydrological monuments around the world and to clarify their compatibility with hydrological monuments in the Sheki-Zagatala region.

References:

1. Aslanov, H.Q. Kürün aşağı axarının ekocoğrafi problemləri. Monoqrafiya. Bakı: Çəşioğlu, 2013, səh. 233. (Aslanov, H.Q. (2013). Eco-geographical problems of the lower reaches of the Kura. Monograph. Bakı: Chashu Oglu). 03.05.2022. Retrieved from <http://web2.anl.az:81/read/page.php?zoom=0&bid=346323&pno=12>
2. “Azərbaycan Respublikası Regionlarının 2019-2023-cü illərdə sosial-iqtisadi inkişafı Dövlət Proqramı”nın təsdiq edilməsi haqqında. Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Fərmanı. İlham Əliyev, Azərbaycan Respublikasının Prezidenti Bakı şəhəri, 29 yanvar 2019-cu il 500. (On approval of the “State Program of socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2019-2023”. Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan. İlham Aliyev, President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Bakı, January 29, 2019, 500). 09.05.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/41320>
3. Azərbaycan Respublikasının Şəki şəhərinin, Balakən, Qax və Zaqatala rayonlarının sosial-iqtisadi inkişafının sürətləndirilməsinə dair əlavə tədbirlər haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Sərəncamı, Bakı şəhəri, 1 iyun 2006-cı il, № 1489 (Order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on additional measures to accelerate the socio-economic development of Sheki, Balakan, Gakh and Zagatala districts of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Bakı, June 1, 2006, № 1489). 28.05.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/12260>
4. Hüseynov A.T. Azərbaycanın su balansını təşkil edən əsas çaylar (İcmal). AMEA-nın Mikrobiologiya İnstitutunun Elmi Əsərləri. UOT 579.2, 2017, № 2. (Huseynov A.T. (2017). The main rivers that make up the water balance of Azerbaijan (Review). Scientific Works of the Institute of Microbiology of ANAS) 30.04.2022 Retrieved from https://azmbi.az/PDF/AMEA%20Mikrobiologiya%20%C4%B0nsti-tunun%20Elmi%20%C6%8Fs%C9%99r1%C9%99ri%202017_15_2.pdf
5. İmanov F.Ə., İsmayılov R.A., Nuriyev A.A. Çayların bərpası və ekoloji axımı. – Bakı: Ecoprint. – 2019. – 96 s. (Imanov F.A., Ismayilov R.A., Nuriyev

A.A. (2019). Restoration and ecological flow of rivers. Ecoprint, Baku)

6. Məhərrəmov, X.C. Azərbaycan ərazisində baş verən dağıdıcı hidrometroloji hadisələr: [dağıdıcı hidrometeoroloji hadisələrin iqtisadi və sosial-coğrafi baxımdan öyrənilməsi] –Bakı: Elm – 2008 – 136 s. (Maharramova, X.C. (2008). Destructive hydrometeorological events in the territory of Azerbaijan. Elm, Baku)

7. Məmmədov Q.Ş. Azərbaycan ekoturizm potensialı. – Bakı: Şərq-Qərb, I cild. – 2012. – 360 s. (Mammadov G.Sh. (2012) Azerbaijan: ecotourism potential. I volume, Sharg-Garb, Baku)

8. Məmmədov M.Ə. Azərbaycanın hidroqrafiyası. – Bakı: Təhsil NPM. – 2012. – 253 s. (Mammadov M.A. (2012). Hydrography of Azerbaijan. Education NPM, Baku)

9. Məmmədov Q., Məmmədova S., Hüseynli E., Həşimov A. Sosial ekologiya (socioekologiya) – Ali məktəblər üçün dərslik – Bakı – 2015 – 675 s. (Mammadov G., Mammadova S., Huseynli E., Hashimov A. (2015) Social ecology (socioecology). Textbook for university, Baku)

10. Nazarova G. (2022). Importance of the ecological environment of the north-western region of Azerbaijan. Annali d'Italia №30 2022, Vol 2, Florence, Italy, 8-11

11. Rəcəbov R.F. Orta Kür çökəkliyi çaylarının bulanıqlıq xəritəsinin tərtibi və təhlili. Bakı Universitetinin xəbərləri, 2013, №2, Təbiət elmləri seriyası. UDK 551.4. (Rajabov R.F. (2013). Compilation and analysis of turbidity map of Middle Kura basin rivers. Baku University News №2, Natural Sciences Series). 01.05.2022. Retrieved from <http://static.bsu.az/w8/Xeberler%20Jurnali/Tebiet%20202013%20202/209-216.pdf>

12. “Alazan/Qanıx çayı hövzəsi üçün Pilot Çay Hövzəsinin İdarəçiliyi Planına dair” pilot layihə. (Pilot Project on Pilot River Basin Management Plan for Alazan / Ganikh River Basin) 06.05.2022. Retrieved from <https://meteo.az/index.php?ln=az&pg=110>

13. 2015 – 2020-ci illərdə Azərbaycan Respublikasında alternativ və bərpaolunan enerji mənbələrindən istifadəyə dair Milli Strategiya üzrə təsirin qiymətləndirilməsi və baza səviyyəsində təhlilə dair Əhatə dairəsinin müəyyənləşdirilməsi üzrə məsləhətləşmələr və seminar (Consultations and workshops to assess the impact of the National Strategy on the Use of Alternative and Renewable Energy Sources in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2015-2020 and to determine the scope of analysis at the base level). 07.05.2022. Retrieved from https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/eia/meetings/2015/May_SEA_workshop_scoping_Baku/12_may.pdf

14. Azərbaycan Respublikası Milli Su Strategiyası (National Water Strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan). 09.05.2022. Retrieved from https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/water/npd/Water_Strategy_Rafiq_Verdiev.pdf

15. Balakən-Zaqatala zonasındakı çaylarda daşqın olub (The rivers in the Balakan-Zagatala zone were flooded). 15.05.2022. Retrieved from <https://az.trend.az/azerbaijan/society/3488294.html>

16. Acınohur gölü niyə quruyur? (Why does Lake Acinohur dry up?) 16.05.2022. Retrieved from <https://qafqazinfo.az/news/detail/acinohur-golu-niye-quruyur-321019>

17. Azərbaycanadakı şlalələr quruyur (Waterfalls in Azerbaijan are drying up). 21.05.2022. Retrieved from <https://aqreqator.az/en/cemiyyet/1569614>